

STUDY OF ADJUSTMENT AND EMOTIONAL COMPETENCE OF PUPIL TEACHERS OF SAMASTIPUR DISTRICT (BIHAR)

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Abstract

Maintaining equilibrium between personal needs and external circumstances is a fundamental process known as adjustment, which is crucial for leading a fulfilling life. This process relies heavily on emotional intelligence, enabling individuals to effectively navigate various social and environmental challenges throughout their lifespan. Recognizing the individualistic nature of adjustment, this study investigated the relationship between adjustment levels and emotional competence in a sample of 300 pupil teachers of Samastipur District of Bihar. Survey method is adopted to collect data from different teacher training colleges of Samastipur District. The findings revealed a significant and positive correlation between these two factors, highlighting the importance of both emotional intelligence and adaptive skills for Pupil Teachers.

Keywords: *Emotional Intelligence, Adjustment, Pupil Teachers.*

1. Introduction

Adjustment is a multifaceted process through which individuals strive to navigate and overcome life's challenges by employing diverse coping mechanisms. It involves maintaining equilibrium between personal needs and environmental constraints. Harmonious adjustment fosters a comfortable existence free from stress, conflict, and frustration (Chauhan, 1984). A pupil teacher's ability to adjust significantly influences their overall development, as academic and home environments often contribute to such challenges. Given the substantial amount of time pupil teachers spend in educational institutions, these settings have a profound impact on

their values, interpersonal relationships, work ethic, productivity, and adaptability. Training Institutions play a crucial role in supporting pupil teachers by providing them with enriching experiences, guidance, instruction, and discipline. This equips them with the knowledge, skills, attitudes, and habits necessary for successful societal integration. Therefore, adjustment not only fulfills individual needs but also aligns with societal expectations. A comprehensive definition of adjustment encompasses a state of well-being where an individual's needs are met in accordance with the behavioral norms of their culture.

Emotional competence encompasses the crucial social skills necessary for recognizing, interpreting, and responding effectively to emotions, both in oneself and others. This proficiency fosters ease in social interactions and empowers individuals to lead and express themselves successfully. Key components of emotional competence include expressing opinions, receiving compliments graciously, and maintaining a positive self-image. Emotional intelligence, a facet of social intelligence, involves the ability to monitor one's own emotions and those of others, discerning nuances and utilizing this information to guide thoughts and actions. Competence, in this context, refers to the mastery of abilities required to perform a task effectively. It allows individuals to express their emotions freely and constructively interact with others. Emotional competence stems from emotional intelligence, which enables the identification and understanding of emotions. As a fundamental set of psychological abilities, it significantly contributes to overall life success. Therefore, emotional competence, also known as emotional intelligence or emotional quotient, equips individuals with the relational skills needed to navigate daily life effectively, both professionally and personally. Developing emotional competence is essential for managing one's own emotions and behavior while interacting constructively with others.

2. Review of Related Literature

Megawati and Wulandari (2019) investigated the relationship between local and migrant students in Malang, Indonesia, finding that a lack of understanding often leads to prejudice and segregation. The study sought to determine if differences in emotional competence existed between these two groups of adolescents (aged 18-22) enrolled in undergraduate programs. Using non-probability sampling, researchers recruited 60 local students and 48 migrant students. Analysis via a TWO-WAY-ANOVA test revealed no statistically significant difference in emotional competence between the two groups ($p > .05$). The researcher suggest that this finding may be attributed to cultural similarities, as many migrant students shared the same Javanese cultural background as their local counterparts.

Sharma (2017) studied; the adjustment experiences of guest faculty teachers employed in government schools within Sirsa District were investigated. The findings revealed statistically significant differences in adjustment levels between male and female guest faculty members, as well as between those working in urban and rural settings within the district's secondary schools.

Sekar and Lawrence (2016) investigated the connection between various aspects of adjustment (emotional, social, educational, and overall) and academic performance among high school students. The research sought to determine if a significant correlation existed between these adjustment factors and academic success. Their findings indicated a statistically significant relationship between all types of adjustment and academic achievement in high school students.

Chaurasia and Gupta (2015) examining the relationship between gender, academic stream, and emotional maturity and adjustment among undergraduate students, findings indicated that female students demonstrated higher levels of both emotional maturity and adjustment compared to their male counterparts. Furthermore, science students exhibited higher scores on the Adjustment Inventory for College Students (AICS), while art students scored higher on the Emotional Maturity Scale (EMS). While no significant differences were observed between males and females in either AICS or EMS scores, a significant difference was found between art and science students in terms of EMS scores, but not in AICS scores.

Neelakandan (2007) investigated the emotional intelligence of school teachers in Cuddalore District, Tamil Nadu, India. The research revealed that primary school teachers demonstrated an average level of emotional competence. Furthermore, it was observed that educators possessing higher qualifications exhibited superior emotional competence compared to those with only essential qualifications. Notably, no statistically significant difference was found in emotional competence levels between government and private school teachers.

3. Rationale of the Study

In contemporary society, emotional intelligence is increasingly recognized as a crucial factor in both professional and personal success. The complexities of modern life, driven by scientific and technological advancements, often present emotional challenges that can significantly impact the teaching-learning process. Teachers play a pivotal role in this process, acting as intermediaries between the educational system and pupils. Emotionally intelligent teachers possess a heightened capacity to perceive, understand, utilize, and manage emotions effectively compared to their counterparts. Emotional competence, a key component of psychological

well-being, encompasses the essential social skills required to recognize, interpret, and respond constructively to emotions in oneself and others. It is rooted in emotional intelligence, which involves the ability to identify emotions accurately. Psychologists emphasize that navigating the rapidly changing world demands more than just intellectual prowess. Individuals need emotional competence to make sound decisions, adapt efficiently to change, develop leadership abilities, foster creativity and collaboration, respond effectively to competition, encourage innovative thinking, and enhance knowledge retention among students. Emotional competence is a learned skill that empowers individuals to manage their emotions and behavior while interacting effectively with others.

Individuals require healthy interpersonal relationships and effective coping mechanisms for optimal well-being. However, various physical, psychological, intellectual, and social factors can influence an individual's ability to adjust, leading to stress. Adjustment involves individuals modifying their behavior and attitudes to align with environmental demands. This ongoing process is crucial for achieving harmony and fulfillment in life. Psychosocial theories suggest a strong link between adjustment, achievement motivation, and emotional competence. Emotional competence, often referred to as emotional intelligence or EQ, encompasses an individual's ability to understand and manage emotions effectively, leading to personal success. Furthermore, robust interpersonal skills fostered through emotional competence play a vital role in promoting adaptive behaviors. The effectiveness of any educational innovation hinges on the quality of teachers who implement it. Therefore, prioritizing the training and development of highly effective educators is paramount for elevating educational standards. Recognizing the significance of learner adjustment, emotional competence, and their impact on well-being, this research aims to investigate these factors within the context of pupil teachers.

4. Statement of the Problem

For the present research, Statement of the Problem has stated as:

“Study of Adjustment and Emotional Competence of pupil teachers of Samastipur District (Bihar)”

5. Operational Definitions

(i) Adjustment

This refers to the adaptive adjustments in behavior required to fulfill needs and address environmental pressures, ultimately enabling individuals to achieve a state of balance and equilibrium with their surroundings.

(ii) Emotional Competence

Emotional intelligence encompasses the capacity to comprehend, regulate, and articulate one's emotions effectively. This skill set enables individuals to successfully navigate various aspects of life, including academic pursuits, interpersonal relationships, problem-solving, and adaptation to the complexities of personal growth and development.

(iii) Pupil Teachers

Pupil Teachers defines as undergraduate students enrolled in teacher training programs within training institutions located in the Samastipur District.

6. Objectives

The following are the objectives of the present study:

1. To find out the level of adjustment and emotional competence among Pupil Teachers of Samastipur District.
2. To find out significant difference among Pupil Teachers in their adjustment and emotional competence with respect to the variables namely: Gender (Male & Female).
3. To find out whether there is any significant relationship of adjustment and emotional competence among Pupil Teachers.

7. Null Hypotheses of the Study

The following are the null hypotheses formulated for the present study:

1. There is no significant difference between male and female Pupil Teachers in their adjustment and emotional competence.
2. There is no significant relationship between adjustment and emotional competence among Pupil Teachers.

8. Method used for Study

Survey method of research is proposed to be used for the present study.

9. Tools used

For the present study, the scales used are,

1. 'Adjustment Scale' developed and validated by Prof. A.K.P. Sinha & Prof. R.P. Singh.
2. 'Emotional Competence Scale' validated by Sharma and Bhardwaj (2013).

10. Population and Sample

The students studying in colleges of teacher education of Samastipur District of Bihar State, considered as the population of the present study. From this population, a representative sample of 300 under pupil teachers were selected by means of stratified random sampling technique. The stratification will be made on the basis of gender of Pupil Teachers.

11. Statistical Techniques

Percentage, Mean and SD, ‘t’ - Test & Karl Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation

12. Analysis and Interpretation

Objective 1: To find out the level of adjustment and emotional competence among Pupil Teachers of Samastipur District.

Table-1: Level of Adjustment and Emotional Competence of Pupil Teachers

Variables	Low		Moderate		High	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Adjustment	72	24	192	64	36	12
Emotional Competence	66	22	185	61.67	49	16.33

The Table-1 displayed that 24% of Pupil Teachers reported low, 64% of them moderate and 12% of them high level of adjustment. Further Table-1 inferred that 22% of Pupil Teachers reported low, 61.67% of them moderate and 16.33% of them high level of emotional competence.

Objective 2: To find out significant difference among Pupil Teachers on the basis of Gender (Male & Female) in their adjustment and emotional competence.

Null Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between male and female B.Ed., Trainees in their adjustment and emotional competence.

Table-2: Mean Score Difference between Male and Female Pupil Teachers in their Adjustment and Emotional Competence

Variables	Gender	Mean	SD	‘t’ value
Adjustment	Male (147)	163.27	5.73	3.95*
	Female (153)	161.53	7.92	
Emotional Competence	Male (147)	159.95	7.73	4.23*
	Female (153)	161.05	8.56	

*At 0.05 level of significance, the table value is 1.96

The above Table-2 inferred that there was significant difference between male and female pupil teachers in their adjustment and emotional competence, as calculated ‘t’ values of 3.95 and 4.23 were higher than the tabulated value of 1.96 at 5% level of significance. While comparing the mean score female pupil teachers showed better adjustment and emotional competence than male. Hence the hypothesis 1 was not accepted.

Objective 3: To find out whether there is any significant relationship of adjustment and emotional competence among Pupil Teachers.

Null Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between adjustment and emotional competence among Pupil Teachers.

Table-3: Relationship between Adjustment and Emotional Competence of the Pupil Teachers

Variables	'Y' Value	Table Value	Nature of Correlation
Adjustment Emotional Competence	0.658*	0.362	Substantial

*At 0.01 level of significance the table value of ' γ ' is 0.362

From the above Table-3 it was concluded that there was significant positive correlation between the adjustment and emotional competence of Pupil Teachers as the calculated ' γ ' value 0.658 were greater than the table value 0.362 at 1% level of significance.

13. Major Findings

1. There was significant difference between male and female Pupil Teachers in their adjustment.
2. There was significant difference between male and female Pupil Teachers in their emotional competence.
3. There was significant positive correlation between adjustment and emotional competence among pupil Teachers.

14. Conclusion

Emotional intelligence, which can be acquired through learning and practice, enables individuals to regulate their feelings and conduct themselves appropriately in social situations. Emotional competence encompasses both understanding and responding to the feelings, requirements, and worries of others. An empathetic individual can perceive the emotions of others and grasp their viewpoints. Adjustment necessitates that individuals modify both their actions and beliefs to conform to the requirements of their surroundings. This continuous process is essential for attaining a state of balance and contentment in life. Within the educational setting, demonstrating genuine concern for pupil teachers fosters a learner-centered approach. This involves anticipating, identifying, and fulfilling the needs of pupil teachers. It is widely recognized that adjustment and emotional competence has a beneficial impact on student learning outcomes.

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